

Work Environment and Work Engagement among Librarians in Universities in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated work environment, and work engagement among librarians in universities in South-South, Nigeria. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population consisted of 210 librarians from university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The researcher studied the entire population because it was small and manageable. The instrument used to collect data was a questionnaire titled “Librarians’ Work Environment, and Work Engagement Questionnaire (LWEWEQ)”. A total of 210 questionnaire were administered and 200 copies were completed, returned and used for the study. This amounts to a 90% questionnaire response rate. The data obtained from the administration of the questionnaire were analysed using frequency, mean and standard deviation, Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient for the research questions and linear regression for the hypothesis. Findings revealed moderate extent of work environment and moderate extent of work engagement. The study concluded that promoting a productive atmosphere is advantageous, as an appealing workplace contributes to better performance. Conversely, an unfavourable work environment can negatively affect the well-being and satisfaction of librarians or staff. It recommended in the study that University management should ensure that librarians in universities in South-South Nigeria have access to adequate workspace, up-to-date facilities, and a positive organisational climate that promotes efficiency and collaboration.

Keywords: Librarians, Work Environment, Work Engagement, Universities, South-South, Nigeria.

Introduction

Work engagement occurs when librarians perceive their daily work tasks as meaningful, have a positive attitude, and are committed, enthusiastic, and passionate about their job. It equips employees with necessary skills to work for the company with specific job roles for desired organizational results, all while being actively involved in their work (Akinola, 2020). Work engagement measures how engaged individuals are in the tasks required for their job and is strongly linked to their job performance (Bakker & Oerlemans, 2019; Martínez et al., 2020). The terms employee engagement and work engagement are often used synonymously. Work engagement pertains to how an employee connects with their work personally, while employee engagement relates to the connection between the employee and their organisation (Tisu et al.,

2020). Libraries are interested in identifying the factors that determine work engagement because of its link to high energy, responsibility, enthusiasm, and effective job connection. The level of enthusiasm employees has for their work is influenced by personal traits as well as aspects of the organisational environment (García-Arroyo & Segovia, 2021). The work environment includes the actual physical location and surroundings of the workplace. The working environment includes both the internal and external surroundings where employees carry out their assigned tasks to achieve the organisation's goals and objectives, like in a library setting. The work setting needs to be conducive for librarians to be productive and content. Yet, inadequately created, incompetently overseen, or ineffectively established work settings can significantly impact employees' productivity. Employees are a vital part of a company and a strong company is one that prioritizes the well-being of its employees (Bhatti, 2018). This is often done by monitoring their work environment, as employees dedicate their lives to working at their workplace.

In this way, the work environment impacts their emotions, thoughts, focus, behaviour, deeds, and abilities. According to Mattson et al. (2016), employee engagement and performance are significantly influenced by the work environment. As stated by Mohammed et al. (2020), in order to stay competitive and successful, organizations must quickly adapt to a changing environment and enable their employees to thrive in the workplace. The environment consists of surroundings that affect humans, whether in physical or non-physical form. The work environment refers to the physical and social conditions in which individuals work to accomplish the organization's objectives. This involves equipment, processes, frameworks, and methods that impact the employees' performance. It could have either a negative or positive effect. Many factors such as work environment, level of motivation, support, and leadership can impact employees' performance (Satyvendra, 2019). The work environment consists of social interactions, power supply, physical facilities, lighting levels, and motivation among colleagues. The workplace atmosphere can hinder or improve job performance for librarians who need a comfortable, suitable, and friendly environment for their work. Thriving employees are seen as a valuable asset that can give organizations a competitive edge, playing a crucial role in their success by performing well, maintaining good health, being proactive, seeking self-improvement, focusing on their career, and giving high priority to organisational objectives (Mohammed et al., 2020).

Research has shown that, out of all the positive qualities effective employees possess, emotional intelligence is a more dependable predictor of overall success than our intelligence quotients. Numerous findings and researchers' opinions agree that the work environment significantly influences the success of any organisation, including libraries, and it is clear that a positive work environment can enhance the performance of librarians. It has been noted that the work environment influences librarians' dedication and success. The research study on self-awareness, self-motivation, and self-regulation regarding emotional intelligence has stigmas and limitations (D'Errico, 2019).

Statement of the Problem

In librarianship, academic librarians must continuously adapt to the evolving needs of users and advancements in technology, making their level of work engagement a critical factor for library efficiency and effectiveness. Work engagement reflects the extent to which librarians are dedicated, motivated, and fully involved in their professional roles. It has become a key focus for

academic library administrators, as it serves as a strong predictor of work outcomes, organisational success, and overall library performance. When librarians are fully engaged in their work, they demonstrate higher levels of creativity and initiative, which drive innovations that contribute positively to the development and advancement of library services. Engaged librarians in university libraries fosters talent retention, enhances users' trust, and boosts performance. Despite the many benefits emanating from work engagement, Oladejo and Kareem (2019) found that librarians in Nigerian university libraries experience low levels of work engagement. What could have resulted to the minimal work engagement of librarians in Nigerian university libraries? Could it be linked to work environment? It is against this backdrop that this study investigated work environment, and work engagement of librarians in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to explore librarians' work environment and work engagement in universities in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study set out to:

1. Determine the extent of the librarians' work environment in universities in South-South, Nigeria;
2. Assess the extent of work engagement among librarians in universities in South-South Nigeria.
3. Examine the relationship between work environment and work engagement of librarians in universities in South-South, Nigeria;

Research Questions

The study seeks to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the work environment among librarians in universities in South-South, Nigeria?
2. What the extent of work engagement among librarians in universities in South-South Nigeria.
3. What is the relationship between work environment and work engagement of librarians in universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Literature review

University libraries are libraries that exist within universities. They serve as collections of knowledge from significant thinkers of both the past and today. Their resources and services aim to enhance the educational programmes of the parent organisations and also offer community support. Libraries are widely acknowledged by scholars (Kasa et al., 2021) as the foundation of tertiary institutions, serving as the central point around which all teaching develops. Thus, it is appropriate to assert that no university can thrive without a quality library, as its core aims include teaching, learning, research, and community services. These cannot be achieved without deeply committed librarians. The complex and heightened competition in 21st century organizations have

resulted in a pressing demand for strategic employee involvement in the worldwide workforce (Satata, 2021).

In contemporary education, academic libraries function as essential centres for acquiring and sharing knowledge, influencing the intellectual endeavours of educational institutions. Librarians, the stewards of these collections, are responsible for coordinating smooth information services and overseeing priceless resources. The work engagement strategy is essential for the continuous survival and sustainable growth of university libraries amidst a progressively challenging academic landscape. Extremely committed employees are vital assets for every organisation. Akinola (2020) characterized work engagement as a state of awareness where employees view their daily tasks as meaningful, maintain a positive outlook toward their employment, and display involvement, commitment, enthusiasm, and passion for their work. It provides employees with the necessary skills to work for the organization, outlining clear job traits for desired organizational results while remaining focused on their tasks.

The work setting or atmosphere can either hinder or boost the efficiency of library staff whose roles necessitate comfortable, supportive, and pleasant surroundings. Although the recognised factors influencing job satisfaction, like the work environment and training, remain relevant, the library is perceived to be losing its status as the primary source of information, which may be linked to inadequate job performance by library staff. The researchers noted that library staff is becoming disinterested in fulfilling their essential roles as academics and researchers, even though there is evidence that a supportive work environment and training improve performance. This can be linked to discontent regarding essential elements in the workplace, including a negative working environment, insufficient staff training, and inadequate internal training provided by the university library management. Librarians' work engagement may not be optimal if the work environment conditions are not favourable, as an improved work environment increases employee productivity. Noise is another dimension of the work environment that impacts employee performance in the workplace.

Some people are sensitive to noise, and for them, the right noise environment is particularly important. The licentiate in technology and sound design expert says buildings need to be designed so that the right sounds are heard, and unwanted sounds are not. Furthermore, with regard to workplace factors and their relationship to employees' work engagement, two main approaches can be distinguished: those that focus on situational factors that enhance and facilitate performance and those that focus on situational factors that hinder performance. Currently, organisations and work as a whole are undergoing dramatic changes that are impacting the conceptualisation and understanding of employee performance. Five main trends are redefining employee professional engagement: the importance of continuous learning, the relevance of proactivity, the increase in teamwork, globalisation, and technology (Sonnentag & Frese, 2017).

Zhang et al. (2021) assumed that components of the work environment are both physical and behavioural in nature. The researchers found that this behavioural environment is the etiquette that officials (employees) must observe among themselves and is interconnected. This shows that the relationship between employees and between employers and employees can have a major impact on overall performance and, therefore, productivity. Service delivery is a function of human needs. That is, without human needs, there may be no need to provide services. believe that information

consultants try to maximise this need, since human behaviour is the process of constantly generating needs and constantly satisfying them. Even though the library is a public institution, the government wants to increase its efficiency and improve service delivery, it should apply business management principles for public administration purposes. Work environment of librarians in developing countries, including Nigeria, remains inadequate compared to that of developed nations due to poor infrastructure, unstable power supply, and limited access to modern technologies. Their study indicated that these environmental constraints negatively affect librarians' performance and efficiency. This implies that, in some contexts, the work environment of university libraries may not be sufficiently supportive, which contradicts the present study's finding of a generally conducive work environment.

Eyo (2021) concluded that working in a stimulating, privileged intellectual environment increases job performance. In this era of modern service delivery in university libraries, applications of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the working environment positively contribute to opportunities to improve and increase the level of performance in the delivery of library services. The working environment of library staff contributes significantly to work performance in university libraries. Work environments are one of the most important existing phenomena in organisations. Comfortable working environments also enable employees to perform at their best. The physical library environment maximises employee performance. However, a poor work environment that led to underperformance of staff resulted in tragedies that resulted in lower results, lower profitability and deterioration in the overall organisational effectiveness of the organisation. The right physical and psychosocial environmental factors increase work performance and engagement. If the management of public university libraries does not care whether an appropriate working environment, staff development and personal variables are provided for library staff to perform their duties, it could affect effective performance and lead to low performance levels of library staff in public universities.

Humphries (2015) reported that creating an appealing, fulfilling, and motivating workplace positively influences employee performance and instils a sense of purpose and pride in their work. Their findings showed that employees working in supportive environments demonstrate higher commitment and productivity. This agreement suggests that a favourable work environment plays a crucial role in promoting effective job performance and engagement among librarians, which is consistent with the current study's finding of a largely supportive work environment. The level of work engagement of library staff at public universities is crucial to achieving the goals set by the library. Many factors, such as motivation, work environment and leadership in the work environment, contribute to the work engagement of library staff. Jones (2019) listed characteristics such as knowledge, experience, skills, abilities, awareness, values, motives and needs that individual bring to the job.

Methods

This research adopted the correlation research design. A correlational research design is regarded as appropriate because it shows how two or more variables are connected to each other. The population of this study is 210 librarians from twenty-five (25) University libraries in South-South, Nigeria. This study involved librarians in Federal and State University libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The sample size of this study is 210. The entire 210 librarians were used as a sample for

the study because the population is considered to be small and manageable. The total enumeration sampling technique was therefore used. The questionnaire is the research instrument used in this study titled “Librarians’ Work Environment, and Work Engagement Questionnaire (LWEWEQ)”. The questionnaire was adapted from validated scientific tools, the Work Environment Scale by Patrick and Kareem (2021).

The data obtained from the administration of the questionnaire were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used to analyse data generated on the demographics section of the questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyse data generated from research questions one, while inferential statistics such as Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) were used to test the hypothesis. Data generated from research questions one and two, were interpreted and answered using the decision rule (1-1.50 Very Low Extent, 1.51-2.50 =Low Extent, 2.51-3.50= Moderate Extent, 3.51-4.50 =Great Extent, 4.51- 5.00 =Very Great Extent). The hypothesis is tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Work Experience of the Respondents

Work Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years	32	16
6-10 years	38	19
11-15 years	54	27
16-20 years	46	23
21 years and above	30	15
Total	200	100

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents based on their years of work experience in university libraries or related institutions of higher learning. The data show that the largest proportion of librarians, 54 respondents (27%), have between 11–15 years of work experience. This is followed by 46 respondents (23%) with 16–20 years of experience, and 38 respondents (19%) who have worked for 6–10 years. Librarians with 1–5 years of experience account for 32 respondents (16%), while those with 21 years and above constitute 30 respondents (15%).The findings indicate that the majority of the librarians have considerable professional experience. Specifically, 130 respondents (65%) have worked for between 11 years and above, suggesting a highly experienced workforce in university libraries in the South-South region of Nigeria. This level of experience is likely to positively influence job performance and productivity, as longer years of professional practice are often associated with enhanced skills, competence, and efficiency in library service delivery.

Table 3: Extent of Work Environment of Librarians in Universities

Table with 9 columns: S/N, Extent of Work Environment, VGE, GE, ME, LE, VLE, Mean, Std. It contains 20 rows of data regarding librarians' work environment perceptions.

Grand Mean 3.27 ST.D = 0.95

Decision Rule: 1-1.50= Very Low Extent (VLE), 1.51-2.50 Low Extent(LE), 2.51-3.50 =Moderate Extent (ME), 3.51-4.50 Great Extent(GE), 4.51- 5.00 =Very Great Extent(VGE).

Determining the extent of the work environment of librarians in universities in the South-South region is presented in Table 4.7. As shown in the Table, the aggregate mean score of 3.27 is higher than the criterion mean of 3.00. This indicates that the extent of the work environment of librarians in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria, is great. An item-by-item analysis using the mean range reveals that items such as enjoying being part of the library because of work description (x̄ = 3.65), close supervision by sectional heads (x̄ = 3.66), willingness to assist colleagues (x̄= 3.66), feeling valued by library management (x̄= 3.69), clearly defined responsibilities (x̄= 3.57), adherence to rules and regulations (x̄= 3.60), integrity in library activities (x̄= 3.65), transparency in management (x̄= 3.80), fairness in enforcement of rules (x̄ = 3.86), warm library ambiance (x̄ = 3.93), good ventilation (x̄= 3.66), and encouragement of novel ideas (x̄ = 3.66) all fall within the great extent category (3.51–4.50).Furthermore, items such as feeling proud to be part of the library (x̄ = 3.19), working hard despite routine tasks (x̄ = 3.26), and motivating infrastructure and physical layout (x̄ = 3.26) were rated at a moderate extent (2.51–3.50). Similarly, the perception that too much is expected within a short time frame (x̄ = 2.07), speaking negatively about colleagues (x̄ = 1.93), supervisors finding fault over petty issues (x̄ = 1.91), and discouragement of new approaches (x̄ = 1.80) were rated at a low extent (1.51–2.50), suggesting that these negative workplace practices are not prevalent. In summary, the findings indicate that librarians generally perceive their work environment as supportive, ethical, transparent, and conducive to productivity.

Table 4:

Table 5: Relationship between Work Environment and Work Engagement of Librarians in Universities

S/N	Variable		Work Environment	Work Engagement
1	Work Environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.984**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
		N	200	200
2	Work Engagement	Pearson Correlation	.984**	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
		N	200	200

α =0.05

The data presented in Table 3 were used to answer Research Question Five, which examined the relationship between work environment and work engagement of librarians in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The result of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis revealed a very strong positive relationship between work environment and work engagement, as indicated by the correlation coefficient (r = 0.984).The relationship was found to be statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance (p = 0.000). This implies that improvements in the work environment are associated with higher levels of work engagement among librarians. In other words, librarians who perceive their work environment as supportive, ethical, and conducive to productivity tend to demonstrate greater energy, enthusiasm, and dedication in their work. Based on this finding, it can be concluded that work environment has a statistically significant and positive relationship with work engagement of librarians in university libraries in South-South,

Nigeria. This underscores the importance of maintaining a favorable work environment to enhance librarians' commitment and performance.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from Research Question One revealed that the extent of the work environment of librarians in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria, is to a great extent. This implies that the work environment in these university libraries is largely supportive and conducive to effective job performance and engagement. A favourable work environment enhances librarians' motivation, satisfaction, and willingness to commit themselves to their duties. Essentially, when librarians operate in an environment that supports their professional roles, provides clear job descriptions, and fosters positive interpersonal relationships, they are more likely to be productive and engaged in their work. The finding is corroborated by Popoola (2015), who found that a supportive work environment is essential for the effective performance of library staff in university libraries. Their findings showed that when librarians are provided with adequate physical facilities, good interpersonal relationships, and supportive organisational conditions, they perform their duties more effectively and efficiently. This supports the present study by affirming that a conducive work environment enhances librarians' job performance and engagement, as observed in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The finding also aligns with that of Humphries (2015), who reported that creating an appealing, fulfilling, and motivating workplace positively influences employee performance and instils a sense of purpose and pride in their work. Their findings showed that employees working in supportive environments demonstrate higher commitment and productivity. This agreement suggests that a favourable work environment plays a crucial role in promoting effective job performance and engagement among librarians, which is consistent with the current study's finding of a largely supportive work environment.

The finding contradicts that of Oladejo and Kareem (2019), who found that academic staff in public universities in Lagos State operated in unfavourable work environments that hindered effective job performance and engagement. Their study showed that poor working conditions, inadequate facilities, and organisational challenges reduced staff motivation and satisfaction. This implies that without deliberate efforts to improve workplace conditions, employees may experience low morale and reduced productivity, a situation that deviates from the current study's finding that librarians in South-South Nigeria largely operate within a supportive and conducive work environment. Similarly, the findings of this study are in agreement with Eyo (2021), who established that appropriate physical and psychosocial environmental factors significantly increase employees' work engagement and performance. Eyo (2021) found that working in a stimulating and intellectually supportive environment enhances employees' enthusiasm, commitment, and willingness to go beyond basic job requirements. Their findings showed that librarians working in environments characterised by safety, adequate resources, and positive interpersonal relationships were more engaged in their work roles. This supports the current study's conclusion that a positive work environment plays a critical role in fostering higher work engagement among librarians in university libraries. However, in contrast, the findings of the present study do not align with the implications of Sonnentag and Frese (2017), who suggested that employee work engagement is increasingly shaped by individual proactivity, continuous learning, and adaptability to technological changes rather than the physical or organisational work environment alone. Their study revealed that while situational factors such as the work environment may influence

performance, personal initiative and job crafting are stronger predictors of sustained work engagement. This implies that librarians may remain engaged even in less favourable environments if they possess high levels of intrinsic motivation and proactive work behaviours, which partially contradicts the present study's emphasis on the dominant role of the work environment. Furthermore, the findings of the current study deviate from the position implied by Oswald (2012), who indicated that work incentives and reward systems, rather than the general work environment, are more critical in determining employee productivity and engagement. Oswald's study revealed that formal and informal motivational structures such as incentives, recognition, and rewards exert a stronger influence on employee engagement than environmental conditions alone. This suggests that even in a supportive work environment, librarians' engagement levels may remain low if incentive systems are weak or absent. This implication contrasts with the present study, which establishes the work environment as a significant predictor of librarians' work engagement in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria.

Conclusion

The results indicate that the work setting significantly impacts the level of engagement among university librarians in South-South Nigeria. An organized and encouraging work atmosphere boosts the enthusiasm and efficiency of librarians. Consequently, creating a positive work environment is a crucial strategy for improving librarian involvement and effectiveness in university libraries within South-South Nigeria. The workplace for librarians can facilitate or hinder their ability to perform effectively. This is due to their need for an accommodating environment, a supportive culture, reliable electricity, adequate ventilation, sufficient space, and an inviting ambiance. Employees respond strongly to the conditions of their work environment. The location where librarians operate must be agreeable and beneficial, while the general circumstances of their work should also be favourable. Promoting a productive atmosphere is advantageous, as an appealing workplace contributes to better performance. Conversely, an unfavourable work environment can negatively affect the well-being and satisfaction of librarians or staff.

Recommendations

In line with the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. University management should ensure that librarians in universities in South-South Nigeria have access to adequate workspace, up-to-date facilities, and a positive organisational climate that promotes efficiency and collaboration.
2. The Nigerian Library Association and university regulatory bodies should advocate for and implement policies that promote librarian welfare and engagement across academic institutions

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